

Blood and Milk PK Sampling Case Report Form (CRF)

PID Date ____/____/____ Time: __: __
(24-hour format)

Infant ID

Mothers capillary HB result ____g/dL | Infant's capillary HB result ____g/dL

Collected By _____

Visit number: 5 (month number 7)

- Pre dose maternal venous blood PK sample
- Day 7 maternal venous blood PK sample
- Pre dose maternal breastmilk PK sample
- Day 7 maternal breastmilk PK sample

Breast sampled: Right Left

5 mL of blood received Yes No

If no specify _____

Centrifugation done in the lab? Yes No Not applicable

If "No" why was is it not done?

Plasma frozen in two aliquots at -80°C Yes No

5 mL of breastmilk received Yes No if no specify _____

Breastmilk frozen in two aliquots at -80°C Yes No

Prepared by: _____ /____/____ :____
Staff initials Signature Date Time

Infant Capillary Blood PK sample

Visit number: 5 (month number 7)

- Pre dose PK
- 24-hour PK
- Day 7 PK
- Day 14 PK
- Day 28 PK

Was mandated breastmilk feeding done? Yes No Not applicable

If yes Time: __: __ (24hrs format)

For sample without mandated feed, indicate approximate time for last feeding: __: __

How long was the child fed for prior to sampling? ____min/hours

If "No" why was is it not done?

CABMILK Study

Appendix 3 B

Filter paper prepared? Yes No Not applicable

If "No" why was is it not done?

Prepared by _____ /_____/____ :____
(Initials) Signature Date Time